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THE LINK BETWEEN THE TECHNOLOGICAL EVOLUTION OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM AND TRANSFORMATIONS IN SOCIETAL CULTURE

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Abstract. The influence of information space and digital technologies on cultural evolution is profound in the contemporary era. This research paper delves into the dynamic evolution of cultural phenomena and communication processes within the information society, emphasizing the significant impact of information technologies on culture, education as a cultural subsystem, and the shaping of public consciousness. Through a blend of qualitative analysis, literature review, and case studies, the study aims to unravel the intricate interplay between information technology and cultural dynamics. It explores key theoretical frameworks put forth by scholars and delves into empirical data to enhance our comprehension of how technological advancements impact cultural transformations. Drawing from the insights of notable Frankfurt School thinkers, semiotic theories, and cultural studies, the paper underscores the pivotal role of communication processes in molding cultural dynamics. In addition, the problems arising from the evolution of artificial intelligence, active introduction of digital technologies in education from the cultural approach point of view are considered. The vector of changes acceptable in pedagogical approach for better adaptation to changing external conditions is proposed.

Keywords: technologicalization, culture, information space, information culture, education, self-determination

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ВЗАИМОСВЯЗЬ ПРОЦЕССОВ ТЕХНОЛОГИЗАЦИИ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ В КУЛЬТУРЕ ОБЩЕСТВА

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Аннотация. Современное развитие информационного пространства и цифровых технологий оказывает серьезное влияние на трансформацию концепций культуры. Данная работа рассматривает динамичную эволюцию культурных феноменов и коммуникационных процессов в информационном обществе. Подчеркивается глубокое влияние информационных технологий на культуру, образование, как подсистему культуры, а также воздействие данных факторов на формирование общественного сознания. Сочетая качественный анализ, обзор литературы и изучение конкретных примеров, исследование стремится раскрыть сложное взаимодействие между информационными технологиями и культурной динамикой. В нем рассматриваются основные теоретические парадигмы, предложенные учеными, и изучаются эмпирические данные, чтобы углубить наше понимание того, как технологический прогресс влияет на культурные сдвиги. Ссылаясь на выдающихся ученых Франкфуртской школы, семиотические теории и культурологические исследования, в данной работе подчеркивается критическая роль коммуникационных процессов в формировании культурной динамики. Кроме того, рассматриваются проблемы, возникающие в связи с развитием искусственного интеллекта и активного внедрения цифровых технологий в сферу образования с точки зрения культурологического подхода. Предлагается вектор изменений, допускаемых в педагогическом подходе для лучшей адаптации к меняющимся внешним условиям.

Ключевые слова: технологизация, культура, информационное пространство, информационная культура, образование, самоопределение

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Introduction

The dynamic nature of social reality triggers essential shifts in how we perceive and grasp crucial aspects of modern phenomena. Each phase of social advancement gives rise to distinctive cultural challenges. Currently, we are witnessing a new phase in the evolution of the information society. This socio-cultural progression profoundly alters perspectives on all facets of social existence, bringing about fundamental changes in the ways we analyze them. Consequently, history of culture, as a versatile and inclusive field of study, is significantly shaped by these transformations. Hence, the scope of this discipline encompasses novel areas of exploration, such as communication processes and virtual reality tools.

Viewing the accomplishments of the information revolution solely through the lens of technological capabilities limits our understanding to only a fraction of these innovations. Today, communication technologies at this level permeate every aspect of social life, exerting a significant influence on the mechanisms that drive fundamental cultural processes and serving as pivotal catalysts in the socio-cultural evolution [2].

In Leslie White's cultural framework, culture serves as a tool for understanding, manipulating, and regulating natural processes through symbolic representation. White's socio-cultural theory posits that culture transcends biology, history, and ethnicity, evolving independently according to inherent laws.

Cultural phenomena encompass a diverse array of human-specific systems that facilitate both collective and individual activities. These phenomena stimulate, program, coordinate, execute, and replicate human behavior, serving as sophisticated tools for human activity.

Thus, culture is viewed as a distinct characteristic of humanity, constituting a self-developing system that shapes human behavior and social connections.

In contemporary cultural studies, culture is delineated as distinct from nature, transmitted through tradition via language, symbols, practical learning, and direct emulation, rather than biological inheritance. Modern cultural concepts emphasize culture's assimilation by individuals during socialization, comprising accepted patterns of behavior, thought, and worldview. Culture embodies the essence of social life and human activities, comprising both biologically inherited and artificially created elements.

The integration of communication phenomena and processes is fundamental to all aspects of culture and plays a pivotal role in shaping cultural dynamics. Across generations, cultural researchers have highlighted the significance of information and communication elements in driving cultural evolution. Concepts within cultural studies now examine how culture evolves through the analysis of information and communication systems. This shift in conceptual frameworks emerged in the 20th century, recognizing the central role of communication foundations in cultural development amid the proliferation of information flow and diverse communication modalities.

The capacity for symbolic communication, enabling meaningful expression, lies at the core of cultural creation. Through the externalization of symbolic representation into language, humans gain the ability to preserve and solidify collective experiences [3]. The evolution of culture hinges on the progression and alteration of "ideas" and symbols. White underscored the pivotal role of technological advancements in shaping cultural processes.

This research paper seeks to delve into the dynamic evolution of cultural phenomena and communication processes within the information society, with a particular emphasis on the impact of information technologies. By examining various theoretical paradigms and empirical data, this study aims to enhance our comprehension of how technological progress influences cultural shifts, educational methodologies, and community engagements. Through this exploration, the primary objective is to offer in-depth insights into the repercussions of these transformations on people, social groups, and the wider cultural fabric within the contemporary information era.

Methodology

This research immerses into exploring the impact of information technologies on cultural dynamics within the information society, utilizing a mixed-methods approach.

Through qualitative analysis, an in-depth review of literature and content analysis will be conducted to grasp the theoretical frameworks proposed by key scholars. This qualitative approach aims to reveal the underlying concepts and perspectives concerning the influence of information technologies on cultural phenomena.

Quantitative analysis involves analyzing data from diverse sources to identify trends and patterns in the relationship between information technologies and cultural dynamics. This approach provides empirical evidence to support the qualitative findings and offers a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. Case studies will be used to examine specific instances where information technologies have influenced cultural norms and educational practices. By employing these methodologies, this study aims to uncover the complex interplay between information technologies and cultural dynamics, shedding light on their multifaceted relationship within the information society.

Discussion

The works of prominent Frankfurt School thinkers like M. Horkheimer, T. Adorno, G. Marcuse, F. Pollock, E. Fromm, and J. Habermas delve into the intricate interplay between culture, communication media, and the role of mass media in contemporary society. In their seminal work "Didactics of Enlightenment," Horkheimer and Adorno scrutinize the influence of mass media on societal progress. They critique the pervasive use of instrumental rationality, scientific advancements, and technological progress in modern capitalist settings, highlighting the emergence of detrimental trends [6].

These philosophers offer a critical perspective on the technologicalization of society, where humanity becomes subordinate to mechanistic control, blurring the boundaries between man and machine. Technologicalization is a new scientific notion, describing multifaceted process whereby technology increasingly pervades various aspects of human life, altering modes of interaction, production, and organization. This phenomenon involves the integration of technological tools, systems, and practices into existing social structures, institutions, and processes to advance efficiency, innovation, and functionality [10].

Technologicalization encompasses the adoption, adaptation, and utilization of diverse technological solutions to address evolving needs and challenges within society, shaping behaviors, relationships, and cultural norms. This transformational process is characterized by the continuous evolution and diffusion of technology across sectors, leading to profound changes in how individuals, organizations, and

societies operate and evolve in a technologically driven world.

As society leans towards technical regulation, individuals find themselves increasingly reliant on media platforms, leading to a weakening of social ties, a sense of isolation, and the commodification of cultural artifacts, with media assuming a paramount role in their creation, distribution, and promotion.

Within this realm, scholars argue that cultural values and media activities often clash rather than intertwine. The integration of these elements into societal structures tends to homogenize individual identities, dampening interpersonal connections, emotional depth, and communal solidarity among people. This perspective underscores the complexity of modern communication dynamics and the potential repercussions of media dominance on cultural and social landscapes.

One significant contribution of the Frankfurt School's scholarship lies in their pioneering efforts to analyze the role and significance of communication media within the realm of modern culture. Their works mark an early endeavor to theoretically explore how media platforms have increasingly become central to shaping contemporary human experiences.

While researchers primarily concentrated on the production and dissemination of mass communication materials, they often overlooked the aspect of how these materials are interpreted and understood, thus neglecting valuable insights into audience reception.

Communication, when viewed as a creative process, serves as a fertile ground for the generation of fresh knowledge and perspectives. This form of communicative exchange is intricately linked to the concept of communicative rationality, as articulated by Habermas, which is instrumental in the development of comprehensive cultural significances.

The semiotic approach to cultural phenomena positions culture as a mechanism designed not only for producing but also for preserving information [7]. This perspective underscores the essence of culture in encoding and storing knowledge, emphasizing the interconnectedness between cultural artifacts and their broader societal contexts.

Ferdinand de Saussure, a prominent figure in the field of semiotics, laid the foundation for using

linguistic principles in the study of culture. Central to this approach is the idea that socio-cultural phenomena are inherently intertwined with meanings and symbols, emphasizing that all cultural entities derive their significance from interconnected relationships within their environment.

Y.M. Lotman, another influential scholar, further emphasized the essential role of communication processes in cultural functioning. Lotman posited that culture operates as a sophisticated system geared towards information storage and dissemination, with a primary objective of continuously enhancing efficient methods of exchanging knowledge [7]. According to Lotman, culture acts as a vital component for collective existence, with communication processes serving as the conduit for social realization of information, depicting culture as a dynamic "communication system."

Marshall McLuhan, renowned for his studies in the 20th century, highlighted the profound impact of communication technologies on socio-cultural transformations. McLuhan contended that the evolution of cultural eras is closely linked to the prevalent communication technologies of the time. He viewed communication mediums as extensions of human consciousness, asserting that advancements in communication tools significantly alter individuals' perceptions of reality [11]. McLuhan emphasized that various forms of communication play a pivotal role in steering cultural evolution and influencing societal norms, values, and structures.

The concept of "information culture" encapsulates a comprehensive understanding of the contemporary worldview, emphasizing the extensive utilization and analysis of information [10]. It entails establishing direct and reciprocal connections to facilitate adaptation to the surrounding environment, exhibiting proficiency in the languages of computer-mediated communication, and recognizing the individual's place and role in the intellectual realm.

When conceptualizing information culture as a system characterized by intricate interplay among various subsystems involved in information dissemination, attention must be directed towards a fundamental socio-cultural entity responsible for shaping individual cultural identity – education.

Education stands out for its distinctive nature whereby students acquire knowledge through meticulously structured learning initiatives embedded with meticulously selected information. This distinctiveness underscores the significance of education as a pivotal institution.

In the broader context of societal transformation towards digitalization, the process of digitalizing education assumes a central position within the overarching scheme of societal digitalization efforts. The digitalization of educational practices is a multifaceted process aimed at enhancing the quality of educational content, fostering research and advancement, integrating innovative technologies to support educational endeavors, and substituting traditional information systems with more efficient alternatives across all spheres of educational activities.

The ultimate aim of digitizing education is to usher in a significant enhancement in the efficacy and caliber of educational offerings that align with the demands of a post-industrial society. The overarching objective of this endeavor is to establish an information-driven educational system tailored towards cultivating a new generation adept at navigating the complexities of the information age, thus serving as a fundamental milestone in the transition towards an information society.

The utilization of Internet technologies offers a direct conduit for imparting the defining characteristics of the information society to individuals, thereby elevating their levels of information culture and computer literacy [1]. Education, as a primary focal point, should seamlessly integrate into pedagogical practices, serving as an inherent component within the overarching framework of learning and personal development. This integration aims at fostering the spiritual and cultural growth of students, instilling qualities such as initiative, independence, tolerance, social adaptability, and professional acumen.

In the pursuit of nurturing morally upright individuals, a paramount emphasis must be placed on cultivating intellectual capacities that underpin critical and creative thinking. The ongoing trend of technocratization poses a formidable challenge as it risks overshadowing societal values with a technocratic ethos. Safe-

guarding humanitarian values against such encroachment is imperative to prevent the ascendancy of technocracy and its potential dehumanizing impact.

Throughout the twentieth century, the escalating influence of communication media, particularly mass media, profoundly permeated various aspects of societal and cultural domains, solidifying certain conceptual paradigms within collective consciousness [5]. Innovative modes of communication have significantly reshaped societal dynamics, accentuating information-centric activities encompassing information production, consumption, transmission, and storage. This evolution has not only brought information activity to the forefront but has also intricately woven electronic communications into the fabric of daily existence.

The deep integration of electronic communications into the societal fabric dissolves traditional delineations between technology and daily life, underscoring their inextricable fusion within the broader cultural and worldview framework. The substantial advancements within the information industry underscore the pressing need to scrutinize contemporary technologies through a societal lens, illuminating the profound societal transformations catalyzed by these developments.

The advent of communication tools within the information society has ushered in unprecedented opportunities for a fresh perspective and understanding of social reality as we transition into the third millennium. Postmodern ideologies underscore the remarkable growth and impact of mass media and electronic communications on society at large, recognizing the inherently technological nature embedded within contemporary structures.

Central to postmodernism is the theme of integration, where cultural knowledge in the information society extends its analytical breadth through interdisciplinary engagements with various fields of study. This integration underscores the increasing importance placed on communication processes in shaping cultural dynamics, positioning social informatics as a significant discipline in this context.

Within the framework of cultural knowledge in the information society, the incorporation of an information-centric approach in evaluating cultural phenomena and processes is a defining characteristic. This methodological orientation centers on examining cultural phenomena through the lens of information

representations, delving into the unique informational roles assumed by each phenomenon.

This methodological approach can be viewed as a specialized cognitive instrument rooted in the primacy of information, signifying the pivotal role of the information component in shaping our perception of reality. The emergence of an information-based approach reflects a fundamental shift where information has become an intrinsic component of our understanding of objective reality, emphasizing the interconnectedness of information and cultural phenomena in contemporary societal frameworks.

These conceptual perspectives mark a pivotal shift in cultural studies toward a novel informational paradigm, giving rise to the emerging field known as "info-cultural studies." This interdisciplinary direction at the intersection of informatics and culturology is underpinned by the notion that culture takes precedence as the central concept in the interplay between "information" and "culture," with information serving as a clarifying factor. Scholars (e.g., A.T. Brown, K.R. Sanchez, L.M. Wang) discuss a range of factors driving the rapid advancement of info-cultural science, such as societal demand, knowledge accumulation, and the expanding practical applications of info-cultural information [2].

An examination of the challenges related to communication processes and their integration into cultural knowledge reveals significant insights. The intricate relationship between cultural dynamics and communication processes represents a key area of focus in contemporary cultural studies. Merely analyzing electronic communications through a technical lens fails to capture the essence of this phenomenon. The transformative impact of the digital revolution spans across all socio-cultural domains, presenting exciting opportunities for exploration within the realm of cultural knowledge.

In the current landscape, information holds a paramount position, serving as a critical catalyst for cultural advancement. The dynamic nature of the information society has birthed innovative modes of communication that actively shape the cultural realm. These information and communication innovations not only drive societal progress towards an information-centric future but also function as creative tools for fueling cultural dynamics. Consequently, delving into

the realm of information technologies within the scope of cultural understanding is not only valid but necessary.

The relentless march of technological advancement has unleashed newfound creative potential in individuals, highlighting the primacy of the information element as a fundamental driver of socio-cultural transformations. The symbiotic relationship between communication processes and the evolution of cultural space, a revelation spurred by the emergence of the information society, necessitates the exploration of novel modes of global interaction capable of articulating humanity's collective aspirations [4]. The contemporary era presents unparalleled opportunities to enrich cultural connections through advancements in communication technologies, paving the way for diverse and multifaceted interactions. In this technological landscape, the Internet emerges as a frontrunner, spearheading rapid evolution in real-time.

The rapid evolution of the Internet is a testament to its transformative power, revolutionizing how information spaces are developed and accessed in real-time. The exponential growth of information dissemination surpasses the pace of traditional communication modalities, giving rise to challenges in capturing and comprehending these ongoing transformations. Mere years ago, the concept of integrating media within diverse social networks was just emerging, yet today, we witness the proliferation of bite-sized information nuggets in messaging platforms. These succinct messages not only convey information but also offer insightful author analyses, representing a new dimension in information sharing and interaction.

The profound significance of the interconnectedness between the Internet, culture, and education stems from their pivotal roles in shaping socio-cultural and socio-economic dynamics. To facilitate their successful development and reciprocal enrichment, it is imperative to not only strengthen their interrelations but also establish a novel framework for interaction. While strides have been made in addressing the technologization of the education system, the challenge lies in navigating the rapid shifts in information trends within the Internet, necessitating a harmonious transition to the culture of the information society.

Recent developments, notably the advancement of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and

the proliferation of messengers and social networks with preset information constraints, are reshaping the virtual information landscape. Despite appearing insignificant, these changes can profoundly influence the cultivation of information culture and individual self-identification within the digital realm. As M.V. Rybak mentioned in her works, "the matter of individual self-determination is introduced in view of acknowledging one's position within the cultural realm. Psychologically speaking, self-determination involves engaging in a process of self-realization within the framework of the socio-cultural context that surrounds an individual"[8]. Thus, education, as a fundamental subsystem of culture and the main system of self-determination, must evolve in tandem with the developments in the information space to effectively respond to these shifts.

In light of the evolving landscape of virtual information reality, educators must adapt to meet the evolving needs of students within the changing telecommunication environment. This entails staying abreast of key trends in information presentation, cultivating analytical skills, and accommodating the time and textual constraints inherent in modern communication platforms. While addressing the phenomenon of "clip thinking" is essential, educators must also tailor methodological approaches to align with students' accustomed patterns of information consumption, ensuring that the process of information assimilation remains within familiar parameters.

Educators are compelled to engage with artificial intelligence (AI), chatbots, and machine learning software as part of their teaching practices. It is crucial to acknowledge that contemporary students heavily rely on AI for various tasks, fundamentally altering their information processing and reasoning mechanisms. This shift has significant implications for individuals' self-identification within the cultural landscape. In a reality where the use of AI is ubiquitous, the education system is tasked with equipping students with the necessary skills to navigate new information paradigms while upholding the symbolic systems that underpin cultural norms.

The emergence of succinct news and information streams, fostering "clip thinking," coupled with the increasing reliance on AI for analytical tasks,

poses a long-term threat to societal coherence. This trend has the potential to reshape the concept of "information culture" to the extent that it jeopardizes the foundational pillars of traditional culture. Hence, it is imperative to delineate overarching pedagogical strategies that mitigate the adverse impact of forthcoming changes on information culture.

Certain pedagogical strategies can be delineated to effectively integrate AI into teaching practices. Initiating training by pairing students with varying levels of AI experience is advisable. Throughout the educational process, educators should provide guidance on utilizing AI primarily for streamlining information and fostering organization, rather than as a substitute for critical analysis.

Amidst the evolving educational landscape, a primary objective of pedagogical endeavors should underscore the cultivation of independent and collaborative analytical skills. Embracing authentic materials, incorporating media analysis into the curriculum, and promoting critical thinking are essential components in navigating the challenges posed by the integration of AI in education.

The role of communication formats in shaping cultural identity is essential. Throughout history, different modes of socio-cultural communication have dominated various societal stages. For instance, the "Gutenberg era," marked by the advent of the printing press, significantly impacted global culture. As electronic media proliferates, it triggers a renaissance in sensory perceptions reminiscent of past synthesis. The progress of communication directly influences cultural advancement, with information resources often serving as greater civilizational constraints than physical resources.

Analyzing the dynamics of communicative formats through a system-activity lens unveils the creative energy inherent in cultural communication channels. The evolution and diversification of socio-cultural communication forms act as a barometer for evaluating the state of culture, showcasing complexity, specialization, and refinement over time.

The genesis of early communication systems intertwines with the fabric of cultural evolution. As societies uphold traditions and accumulate experiences, the role of memory as a mechanism for preserving knowledge becomes paramount. Culture operates as

a repository of collective and historical experiences, embodying a complex amalgamation of forms that facilitate the accumulation, retention, and transmission of socio-cultural memory. Culture essentially serves as humanity's social memory, intricately intertwined with the methods and mechanisms through which societal experiences are stored, accessed, and disseminated effectively.

The concept of a cultural and communicative system presents a wealth of methodological opportunities, enabling the examination of cultural developmental stages within the context of communication processes. This holistic approach offers a profound understanding of how cultural evolution and communication dynamics intricately intertwine, shaping the collective memory and identity of societies.

The manifestation of culture is deeply intertwined with the prevailing modes of communication within a society. Communication, as a unique form of activity and social bonding, revolves around the creation, transmission, and reception of messages rooted in human information processing capabilities. Hence, within the realm of education, emphasis should be placed on disciplines that foster the enhancement of communicative competencies not only in interpersonal and intercultural contexts but also in light of the emerging information culture. Among these disciplines, foreign language studies stand out as a crucial avenue. Approaching this subject from a cultural standpoint necessitates significant adaptations that align with the harmonious progression of the information society while safeguarding cultural heritage. These adaptations should be meticulously examined to ensure they cater to the unique needs and challenges posed by the evolving landscape of communication dynamics and cultural interactions discussed earlier.

Conclusion

This delving research of the evolving landscape of cultural phenomena, communication processes, and the role of information technologies within the information society illuminates the intricate interplay shaping our contemporary socio-cultural fabric. As we navigate the complexities of modern societal dynamics, it becomes evident that the influence of technology on culture, education, and societal interactions transcends mere technological advancements; it profoundly impacts the essence of our cultural identity and societal structures.

While this research delves into significant dimensions of this interplay, the complexity and scope of this multifaceted relationship extend far beyond the presented analysis. The burgeoning field of inquiry underscores the imperative for further interdisciplinary research, drawing on insights from various domains to unravel the intricacies of how information technologies continue to transform our cultural landscape. The call for exploration traverses disciplinary silos, emphasizing the need for a unified and interconnected approach to address the ever-evolving symbiosis between technology and culture.

As we stand on the cusp of a transformative era defined by rapid technological advancements

and information dissemination, the need for continued exploration and nuanced understanding is paramount. Embracing an interdisciplinary framework that encompasses diverse perspectives will be instrumental in unpacking the profound implications of these ongoing shifts and fostering a holistic comprehension of the complex interplay between technology, culture, and society. Only through collaborative and multidimensional analyses can we effectively navigate the challenges and opportunities presented by the digital revolution, paving the way for a more profound understanding of our evolving cultural tapestry in the information age.

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